

Table 1. Personal characteristics for suicide and unexpected deaths other than suicide in Japan, 2011-2014.

Personal characteristics		Suicide		Unexpected death other than Suicide	
		N	%	N	%
Total		159,490	100.0%	115,072	100%
Age	0-20	4,607	2.9%	1,804	1.6%
	21-40	30,767	19.3%	4,373	3.8%
	41-60	43,983	27.6%	10,526	9.1%
	61-80	52,186	32.7%	42,876	37.3%
	81-	26,583	16.7%	55,169	47.9%
	data missing	1,364	0.9%	324	0.3%
	Mean / SD	58.5yo	20.6yo	75.5yo	17.3yo
Sex	Male	103,893	65.1%	63,594	55.3%
	Female	55,597	34.9%	51,478	44.7%
Job	Agriculture	9,550	6.0%	8,701	7.6%
	Self-employed	13,191	8.3%	7,040	6.1%
	Company	34,472	21.6%	14,987	13.0%
	Other	17,312	10.9%	8,596	7.5%
	Unemployed	66,639	41.8%	64,682	56.2%
	data missing	18,326	11.5%	11,066	9.6%

Table 1 (cont.). Personal characteristics for suicide and unexpected deaths other than suicide in Japan, 2011-2014.

Personal characteristics		Suicide		Unexpected death other than Suicide	
		N	%	N	%
Marital Status	Married	65,500	41.1%	50,548	43.9%
	Divorced	43,250	27.1%	14,760	12.8%
	Widowed	28,082	17.6%	40,336	35.1%
	Separated	20,765	13.0%	8,823	7.7%
	Other	1,893	1.2%	605	0.5%
Area	City Area	137,761	86.4%	101,043	87.8%
	Rural Area	21,729	13.6%	14,029	12.2%